

Structural and pH-metric Studies of the Thiosemicarbazone Complexes of Copper(II), Nickel(II), Cobalt(II) and Zinc(II)

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Manuscript received 24 July 1984, revised 29 January 1985, accepted 11 September 1985

Complexes of Cu^{II} , Ni^{II} , Co^{II} and Zn^{II} with 4-*N*-(2,6-dimethylphenyl)-1-*N*-(2-hydroxybenzal)-3-thiosemicarbazone have been prepared. Structures of the complexes have been established by elemental analysis, magnetic moments, conductivity, uv and ir spectra. It is concluded that the ligand is bonded through sulphur, nitrogen and oxygen. Irving-Rossotti pH titration technique is used to calculate proton-ligand and metal-ligand stability constants in 60% (v/v) aqueous dioxane media

THE thiosemicarbazone which comprises a well known group of nitrogen and sulphur donors have been extensively used for complex formation in recent past¹. However, hydroxybenzaldehyde thiosemicarbazone have been comparatively less studied. The present communication reports 2-hydroxybenzaldehyde -4-substituted-3-thiosemicarbazone and their complexes with Cu^{II} , Ni^{II} , Co^{II} and Zn^{II} metal ions. The structure of complexes have been established using analytical, conductance, magnetic measurements, ir and electronic spectral data.

Experimental

All reagents used in the present work were of A.R. grade. The ligand, 4-*N*-(2,6-dimethylphenyl)-1-*N*-(2-hydroxybenzal)-3-thiosemicarbazone (DPHBT) was synthesised by the method of Gingras and Sirianni².

The aqueous solution of metal acetate and dioxane solution of ligand were mixed in 1 : 2 ratio. The sodium acetate buffer was used to maintain pH 6.5. The complexes formed immediately. The reaction mixture digested for 1 h on water-bath to

ensure complete complexation, was then filtered, washed thoroughly with water, followed by dioxane to remove excess metal ion and reagent. The complexes were dried in vacuum over anhydrous calcium chloride.

The complexes were analysed for metal, nitrogen and sulphur by standard methods³⁻⁵. The molecular weights were determined by Rast's method.

The solution of ligand was prepared in purified dioxane while metal nitrates were prepared in double-distilled water. pH-metry method was used to determine the metal-ligand and proton-ligand stability constants. Three solutions were prepared in 3 : 2 (v/v) dioxane-water solvent and titrated against 0.2 M KOH solution at room temperature. A mixture of 0.1 M HNO_3 (2 ml), KNO_3 (5 ml), ligand (10 ml), 0.01 M metal solution (1 ml) and dioxane (14 ml) and water (8 ml) was used in the first titration, the second was without metal and the third without metal and ligand.

Results and Discussion

The elemental analysis of complexes (Table 1) indicate that their composition may be represented

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL, CONDUCTANCE AND MAGNETIC SUSCEPTIBILITY DATA

Sl. no.	Ligand/complex	Mol. wt. Found/Calcd.)	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			Λ Ω^{-1}	μ_{eff} B.M.
			N	S	M		
1.	DPHBT	302.50 (299.00)	13.98 (14.05)	10.72 (10.70)	—	5.36	—
2.	(DPHBT) ₂ Cu	663.81 (659.54)	12.87 (12.74)	10.00 (9.70)	9.77 (9.62)	8.58	2.12
3.	(DPHBT) ₂ Ni	653.71 (654.71)	12.93 (12.83)	9.90 (9.78)	9.00 (8.96)	8.80	2.43
4.	(DPHBT) ₂ Co	650.72 (654.93)	12.80 (12.82)	9.90 (9.77)	8.59 (8.99)	7.85	2.79
5.	(DPHBT) ₂ Zn	663.85 (661.37)	12.75 (12.70)	9.88 (9.68)	9.15 (9.88)	7.58	Diamag.

as ML_n (M =metal, L =ligand). All the complexes are stable at room temperature and are insoluble in most common organic solvents except DMF. The DMF solution of complexes at $1 \times 10^{-3} M$ showed electrical conductance in the range $5-10 \Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ (Table 1) indicating non-ionic nature.

Magnetic susceptibility: The magnetic moment values of the complexes (Table 1) indicate them to be distorted octahedral. The Zn^{II} complex is diamagnetic and it may be tetrahedral. The high values of magnetic moments are due to spin-orbit coupling and may be due to equilibrium between octahedral and square planar structure.

Electronic spectra: The Cu^{II} complex gives λ_{max} at 410 and 500 nm. The bands may be due to ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2E_g$ and ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{1g}$ transitions⁶. The band is with shoulder due to Jahn-Teller distortion. The Co^{II} complex gives λ_{max} at 300, 410, 425 and 500 nm. The first band is due to ligand spectra, and the other bands may be assigned to ${}^4A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4E_g$, ${}^4A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}$ and ${}^4A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4B_{1g}$. The Ni^{II} complex gives λ_{max} at 300, 390 and 420 nm. The Zn^{II} complex does not show any transition band beyond 400 nm.

Ir spectra: The ir spectra of all the complexes show absence of band at 3600 cm^{-1} which is observed in the ligand. It indicates that OH group of salicylaldehyde has taken part in bond formation. The other bands are observed at ~ 1900 ($C=S$), $\sim 1200 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ ($C-O$), ~ 1580 ($C-N$) 550 ($M-N$) and 430 cm^{-1} ($M-O$). The structure of complex is assigned as (where, $M=Cu^{II}$, Ni^{II} , Co^{II} and Zn^{II}),

Stability constants: The practical proton-ligand stability constant for the ligand was calculated with the help of \bar{n}_A values at different B values. \bar{n}_A is calculated by Irving-Rossotti⁶ method as adopted by Jabalpurwala *et al.*⁹. Plot of $\log \bar{n}_A/(1-\bar{n}_A)$ vs B

is done to obtain a best straight line, from which the value of practical stability constant was obtained using the relation,

$$\log pK_1^H = B + \log \bar{n}_A / (1 - \bar{n}_A)$$

The proton-ligand stability constant is found to be 9.27. For metal-ligand stability constants, \bar{n} and pL were calculated⁶. To obtain $\log K_1$, $\log K_2$ and $\log \beta_2$, different computational methods, such as half-integral, point-wise, linear plot¹⁰ and least square¹¹ methods were used. The values of average stability constant are given in Table 2. For $\log K_1$, it is observed that the order of the stability constants are $Cu > Co > Ni > Zn$. Thus, Irving-Williams rule is not violated except for Ni^{II} which forms less stable complex.

TABLE 2—METAL-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS

$\mu = 0.125 M KNO_3$			
Metal ion	$\log K_1$	$\log K_2$	$\log \beta_2$
Cu^{II}	9.08	8.40	17.48
Ni^{II}	5.58	4.54	10.12
Co^{II}	8.78	6.74	15.52
Zn^{II}	5.17	3.12	8.29

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Prof. K. A. Thaker, Head of the Department of Chemistry, Bhavnagar University, for facilities.

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